

``Work Life Balance Of Women Employees: A Bird Eye View``

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Abstract

On The concept of work-life balance is based on the notion that paid work and personal life should be seen less as competing priorities than as complementary elements of a full life. This initiative was aimed at encouraging employers to adopt flexible working arrangements such as job sharing, flexi-time, compressed hours and others, to help their employees to achieve a better balance between the demands of paid employment and those arising from there. The way to achieve this is to adopt an approach that is "conceptualized" as a two way process involving a consideration of the needs of employees as well as those of employers. In order to engage employers in this process it is important to demonstrate the benefits that can be derived from employment policies and practices that support work-life balance, and the scope that exists for mitigating their negative effects on the management of the business. This article would highlight the various values, attitudes & beliefs of women regarding job anxiety in their formal work organizations & particularly balancing their work & personal life. Work Life Balance (WLB) is not a new concept

Keywords: Work-Life Balance, Flexible Working, Demands of Employment, Encouragement.

Introduction

Work-life balance is about improving people's quality of life and widening access to paid employment and career opportunities. A work-life balance ethos supports staffs who wish to have a greater involvement in public life and in the community. It sends a positive message to students with caring responsibilities and promotes positive values to the rest of the students. Working more flexibly can contribute to reducing traffic and pollution thus reinforcing the commitment of the university to the local environment. It can be concluded that supporting and further developing work-life balance policies and practices is important to the university as it presents a series of benefits both for the institution and its employees. For this reason the Directorate of Human Resources has carried out a university-wide staff audit to gain information in order to ensure that work-life balance policies and practices are consistently implemented, match the needs of staff and are compatible with the operational requirements of the university. The following section of this report explains how the audit was carried out and provides an in-depth analysis of its main findings.

Work-life balance policies and practices are also instrumental to ensure that some important economic goals are achieved particularly with regard to women's employment and earnings. The European Union has set a goal of increasing the number of women in work to more than 60% by 2012 (The Social Situation in The European Union, 2001). Although the domestic figures show that the India is well ahead of this target, as overall 67% of women and 79% of men aged between 16 - 64 are in employment, there is still a significant gap between the percentage of men and women with dependent children who are in employment, 89% and 65%

respectively. The gap widens considerably when one looks at the percentage of women in employment whose youngest child is aged 5 or under, in this instance only 53% work, and many of those do so on a part-time basis (Equal Opportunity Commission, 2003). Women's interrupted and patchy employment history has a detrimental effect on pension entitlements and leads to a high level of female poverty in old age. Therefore there is a compelling case for helping women to remain in employment throughout the years of child rearing by offering working pattern that are compatible with their childcare responsibilities

Need of the study

Times have changed. From the time the husband earned, and the wife stayed at home. To the time now when the husband earns and the wife earns too. But the wife still cooks and washes and runs the house. So, how does she balance her work with life at home? Although, over the years women in India have struggled to establish an identity & create a mark in the social as well as in the organizational platforms, but with educational institutions training more and more women to enter professional careers, have drastically changed the scenario. Infact, between 1991 and 2001 female employment in India on the whole, have increased by 3.6% per annum. Within the professional world, which reflects India's small but growing middle class more than the country as a whole, the phenomenon of Indian women "breaking through the glass ceiling" is perhaps more muted. Even, despite legal provisions made by acts like those of the Equal Remuneration Act of 1976 (which promulgates equal payment for equal work, regardless of gender & prohibits gender discrimination in hiring practices), the so-called "glass ceiling" is perhaps still very prevalent within organizations. This is the need of the study.

Review of Literature

The existing studies are very few and very little information is available about the Work life balances usage on various tools.

Research conducted by IES (Kodz et al., 2008) prior to the implementation of the right to request flexible working, nonetheless, indicates some of the other reasons why employees may not wish to change their working arrangements.

The first Work-Life Balance Baseline Study was conducted in 2008 by IFF on behalf of the Department of Education and Employment (Hogarth, et al, 2009).. The study's aim was to assess the extent to which employers operated work life balance practices and whether employees felt existing practices met their needs. The first Flexible Working Life Balances Employee Survey was carried out between September 2008 and February 2009, between six and 11 months after the right to request flexible working was introduced in April 2007 (Palmer, 2009). The second Flexible Working Life Balances on Employee Survey was conducted in January 2005 (Holt and Grainger, 2005). It aimed to monitor changes in the awareness and take-up of the right to request flexible working since the first flexible working employee survey, and to assess the impact of the legislation

Objectives of the Study

This article would highlight the various values, attitudes & beliefs of women regarding job anxiety in their formal work organizations & particularly balancing their work & personal life. Work Life Balance (WLB) is not a new concept

Meaning and concept of the Work Life Balance

Let's first define what work-life balance is not. Work-Life Balance does not mean an equal balance. Trying to schedule an equal number of hours for each of your various work and personal activities is usually unrewarding and unrealistic. Life is and should be more fluid than that. Your best individual work-life balance will vary over time, often on a daily basis. The right balance for you today will probably be different for you tomorrow. The right balances for you when you are single will be different when you marry, or if you have children; when you start a new career versus when you are nearing retirement. There is no perfect, one-size fits all, balance you should be striving for. The best work- life balance is different for each of us because we all have different priorities and different lives. However, at the core of an effective work-life balance definition are two key everyday concepts that are relevant to each of us. They are daily Achievement and Enjoyment, ideas almost deceptive in their simplicity. Engraining a fuller meaning of these two concepts takes us most of the way to defining a positive Work-Life Balance.

The change in the pattern of work and the concept of the workplace after the industrial revolution in the second half of the 18th century gave a new dimension to the concept of WLB. As time progressed, nuclear families increased. A later change was the fading away of the "ideal home" in which the earning member's spouse took care of the home. With improved education and employment opportunities today, most homes are ones in which both parents work, because of necessity and the desire to augment incomes. The need to create congenial conditions in which employees can balance work with their personal needs and desires became a factor that companies had to take note of both to retain them as well as to improve productivity. It was a compulsion that they couldn't afford to ignore. Having realized that, companies started introducing schemes to attract and retain employees and improve their productivity.

Why Work Life Balance is Important to Women?

Today's career women are continually challenged by the demands of full-time work and when the day is done at the office, they carry more of the responsibilities and commitments to home. The majority of women are working 40-45 hours per week and 53% are struggling to achieve work/life balance. Women reported that their lives were a juggling act that included multiple responsibilities at work, heavy meeting schedules, business trips, on top of managing the daily routine responsibilities of life and home. "Successfully achieving work/life balance will ultimately create a more satisfied workforce that contributes to productivity and success in the workplace." Employers can facilitate WLB with many schemes that can attract women employees and satisfy their needs.

Some of these are

1. Facilities for child care
2. Financial planning services for employees who need them
3. Flexi-timings
4. Work sharing
5. Part time employment
6. Leave plans - both paid and unpaid - to suit employee's needs
7. Subsidized food plans
8. Insurance plans
9. Counseling services for problems like managing work and the home
10. Rest rooms, food preparation services
11. Jobs with autonomy and flexibility
12. Realistic workloads
13. Review of work processes to see if the burden on employees can be lightened Maintaining dialogue with the employees and considering their suggestions on a continuous basis

Work-life balance

Can women be both sharers and careers often, working women drop out of the work force when they are doing well, simply because they wanted to stay at home with their children, or care for an ageing parent. Or for both reasons. And then there are women who have children later in life because they want to work for reasons of personal satisfaction or for the money. So, can a woman have it all? The working woman should refuse to take on too much. She should adopt a sense of priorities. If she has children, she should teach them to share responsibilities. But what about the husband? Has he changed at all anywhere in the world?

Surprisingly, a survey in the UK revealed that a majority of men want a 50/50 partnership with their wives both at work and home. They no longer see themselves as macho men. They want to spend more time with their children. Has the Indian man kept pace with the times? Can women achieve a work-life balance? The changing Equations of New Era The Changing Equations The Machine Age The Industrial Age The Networked Age Stress High Higher Highest Work- Life balance You went to work-life started only when you go home Not only are people working at work, but also at home 24-hour workdays split into compartments dedicated for 'life' Women and Work The men worked and women tended the house Both men and women worked, and women still tended the house Both men and women work and tend to the house.'

Framework for successful Work-Life Balance in organizations

1. Identify the key need or reason for introducing Work-Life Balance policies
2. Build the commitment to Work-Life Balance Policies into the organization 's vision or value statement
3. Set up Work-Life Balance Task Force Examine current practices in the organization.
4. Hold joint discussions with employees to evolve policies, while also identifying possible barriers.
5. Communicate policies through handbooks, newsletters, Intranet and other forms of communication.
6. Hold workshops to help Managers implement and manage policies
7. Begin with a few "quick win" policies

Monitor implementation and put feedback systems into place In India, there is a starting point in that organizations have recognized the need for and value of Work-Life Balance policies. An integral part of our lives is our profession. Just as there is responsibility and opportunity in life, our careers are also guided by opportunities and responsibilities. We must ensure that these two factors don't work at cross purposes. Quality of life is something we all covet, every profession affects

life in general and every profession has a duty towards life.

Top Five Strategies to Strike a Balance

1. Budget your time both in and out of the office - Schedule your time efficiently at work. Put yourself on your calendar and take some time for you and your family / friends. Leave work on time at least three days per week - There are times when working late just can't be helped, but schedule your time to leave on time three days per week.
2. Control interruptions and distractions - Stay focused while in the office, and budget your time effectively. Try to schedule a block of time during the day without meetings when you can focus on your tasks with minimal interruptions.
3. Explore the availability of flex-time - Research flex-time options within your organization. If available, it may be a helpful solution.
4. Seize the weekend - Plan your time off as you plan your work week.
5. Schedule activities with family and friends, a weekend trip, or just something fun. Make your time away from work count!

Suggestion

This is hard for a lot of people, because their work is an important part of who they are as people. This can be admirable, especially when you accomplish great things in your work, but an always-on-the-job attitude can be harmful in the long run. The most important thing it is to make a good schedule and keep to it. Block out all your work and non-work commitments and make sure to allow plenty of downtime and non-work time. Treat non-work commitments as seriously as you treat working commitments — the time you've assigned to family, housework, and your own activities needs to be just as inviolable as the time you spend in the office, going to meetings, or meeting deadlines. a) Looking undependable, b) upsetting someone, or c) missing out on something. Make a point of seriously considering any request that comes your way, and double-check your schedule before taking anything else on. Drop the list for a day or two, and take things as they come. This is really about attitude, drawing a clear line between your work-life and the rest of your life. The idea is to give yourself a set amount of time — say, an hour — to do the job, no matter how poorly. Let go of your perfectionism and just do as well as you can in the set time. You may have to go back and fix it up — but you'll be charged up by knowing the "heavy lifting" is already done.

I learned this the hard way when a rough patch of work started to alienate me from my family. Let the people closest to you know what's going on in your work life when things get hectic, so they

don't feel like your lowest priority or worse, suddenly abandoned.

Conclusion

Working women, getting caught in the work/life balance trap will continue to be an ongoing challenge. Careful planning and personal effort is the advice from those who have found balance in both career and home life. As one respondent summarized, "Plan, prioritize and schedule as efficiently as possible... and don't be afraid of hard work!" Work-life balance is a person's control over the conditions in their workplace. It is accomplished when an individual feels dually satisfied about their personal life and their paid occupation. It mutually benefits the individual, business and society when a person's personal life is balanced with his or her own job. The work-life balance strategy offers a variety of means to reduce stress levels and increase job satisfaction in the employee while enhancing business benefits for the employer. In our increasingly hectic world, the work-life strategy seeks to find a balance between work and play. A sentence that brings the idea of work life balance to the point is: "Work to live. Don't live to work."

Companies have begun to realize how important the work-life balance is to the productivity and creativity of their employees who were more favorable toward their organization's efforts to support work-life balance also indicated a much lower intent to leave the organization, greater pride in their organization, a willingness to recommend it as a place to work and higher overall job satisfaction. Employers can offer a range of different programs and initiatives, such as flexible working arrangements in the form of part time, casual and telecommuting work. More proactive employers can provide compulsory leave, strict maximum hours and foster an environment that encourages employees not to continue working after hours. It is generally only highly skilled workers that can enjoy such benefits as written in their contracts, although many professional fields would not go so far as to discourage workaholic behaviour. Unskilled workers will almost always have to rely on bare minimum legal requirements.

References

1. Casebourne, J., Regan, J., Neathey, F. and Tuohy, S (2006), "Employment Rights at Work: Survey of Employees 2005" Employment Relations Research Series No. 51.DTI. <http://www.dti.gov.uk/files/file27222.pdf>
2. DfEE (2000), "Work-Life Balance: Changing Patterns in a Changing World" Department for Education and Employment, London (DfEE).
3. DTI, Stevens, J., Brown, J. and Lee, C. (2004) "The Second Work-Life Balance Study" Employment Relations Occasional Paper
4. Employment Relations Research Series No. 39. "The Third Work-Life Balance Employee Survey: Technical report" DTI. <http://www.dti.gov.uk/files/file11441.pdf> ICM (2007)
5. Employment Relations Occasional Paper, DTI. (URN 07/716) Kodz, J., Harper, H. and Dench, S (2002), "Work-Life Balance: Beyond the Rhetoric" IES report 384. IES.
6. Hogarth, T., Hasluck, C., Pierre, G., Winterbotham, M. and Vivian, D. (2001) "Work-Life Balance 2000: results from the Baseline Study" Research Report RR249. DfEE.
7. Holt, H. and Grainger, H. (2005) "Results of the Second Flexible Working Employee" <http://www.dfes.gov.uk/research/data/uploadfiles/RR249.PDF>
8. Maher, J. and Green, H. (2002) Carers 2000. London: The Stationery Office Palmer, T. (2004) "Results of the first flexible working employee survey"
9. Results from the Employees' Survey. Employment Relations Research Series No. 27. DTI. <http://www.dti.gov.uk/files/file11499.pdf>